

Lessons from Digital Life Norway 2016-2026

- On operating a virtual research centre –
- On building a national research community –
- On integrating computational methodologies and biotechnology –
- On transforming a research and innovation subsystem –

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Executive Summary

The **Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN)** was launched in 2016 as a national initiative to strengthen biotechnology research and innovation through integration with computational sciences, social sciences and humanities, and responsible research and innovation (RRI). Designed as a collaborative, distributed centre rather than a single institution, DLN connected major Norwegian universities and research organisations under the Research Council of Norway’s BIOTEK2021 programme. Over ten years, DLN aimed to build a cohesive research community, foster interdisciplinarity, and support Norway’s transition toward digitally integrated life sciences.

Achievements. DLN demonstrated that a virtual national centre can deliver valuable services, especially to an engaged cadre of hundreds of early-career researchers. Its competence hub provided innovation guidance for early-stage research, advanced data management aligned with FAIR principles, and RRI support. The DLN research school became the largest research school in Norway, creating a strong early-career network and offering courses on interdisciplinarity and societal dimensions of research. DLN also facilitated industry internships, thematic workshops, and cross-project collaborations, strengthening national networks and promoting a culture of innovation. While DLN created scientific networks and helped embed computational approaches and interdisciplinarity in Norwegian biotechnology, the full impact on systemic transformation will require long-term evaluation.

Lessons Learned. Several lessons stand out from DLN’s experience:

- 1. Operating a Virtual Research Centre.** DLN showed that a geographically distributed centre is challenging to operate at a national scale across institutions and disciplines. Such centres require clear financial commitments and organizational anchoring to overcome administrative issues and ensure continuity. DLN also revealed unmet needs—such as innovation support for low Technology Readiness Levels and advanced data stewardship—that future initiatives could address across research domains.
- 2. Building a National Research Community.** The research school proved highly effective in creating a vibrant early-career community with a shared identity. Flexible, small-scale funding for workshops and seed projects also stimulated collaboration and should be considered essential tools for community building. Engagement at senior levels was somewhat more limited, suggesting that voluntary participation alone may not suffice for deeper integration.

3. Integrating Computational Methodologies and Biotechnology. Targeted funding successfully produced high-quality interdisciplinary projects. However, broader structural change requires more than project-level support; it depends on coordinated efforts and strong institutional engagement. Funding bodies and host institutions need to work in tandem to sustain momentum.

4. Transforming a Research and Innovation Subsystem. DLN’s experience suggests that transformation cannot rely solely on building a guiding “lighthouse.” It requires clear mandate and authority, long-term institutional commitments, and alignment of incentives. Future initiatives should embed these elements from the outset to achieve lasting impact.

In summary, DLN leaves a legacy of community building and proof-of-concept for interdisciplinary integration. Its lessons highlight opportunities for replication and improvement in future national and international efforts to modernise research and innovation systems.

About 80 members participated in the 3rd annual conference of Digital Life Norway Research School held at Bekkjarvik outside Bergen in 2019. The DLN research school had over 500 members and was one of the largest research schools in Norway, with many courses and activities oversubscribed.

Preface:

The Context of this Report

The Centre for Digital Life Norway (DLN) was established in 2016 as a national centre for biotechnology research, education and innovation as a response to a policy initiative and subsequent funding initiatives taken by the Research Council of Norway (RCN). These initiatives were designed and implemented by the BIOTEK2021 programme, which was one of the main responses of RCN to the National Biotechnology Strategy 2011-2020 by the Norwegian government.

In 2025, after ten years of operation, one major part of the RCN funding for DLN - the so-called network project or competence hub – came to an end. For DLN participants, this was seen as a moment to reflect, learn and look forward. Accordingly, a process was set up to articulate and analyse the “legacy” of DLN, to prepare for future initiatives and actions, but also to provide advice to other researchers and research funders who might embark on ventures similar to DLN, both within and outside the field of biotechnology and life science.

This report aims to summarise key experiences and lessons learned in DLN during the period 2016-2025. Importantly, it builds on the results from a three-day event in Trondheim 1-3 April, 2025, called the Digital Life Legacy workshop. The workshop gathered nearly 40 researchers, research administrators and research policy professionals, and it followed a structured process designed to harvest outcomes and reflect on DLN’s legacy. Furthermore, the participants were asked to identify which aspects of that legacy are worth preserving within Norway’s R&I ecosystem and suggest pathways for their uptake by other organisations.

The legacy event and its subsequent report (Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2025) as well as this report mark the end so far to what has become a hallmark of DLN, namely dedication of time and resources to a concomitant reflection and learning process as an intrinsic part of centre activities. This process included a designated academic research project ([Res Publica](#)), a search conference in 2018 designed by that research project (Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2018), and a mid-term self-assessment exercise in 2019 (Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2019), as well as other minor events and workstreams. A substantial shift of emphasis in the second funding cycle, from 2021

onwards centre activities pivoted towards knowledge transfer and capacity building for innovation. The last funding cycle (DLN 2.0) coincided with the funding of the Innovation Roadmap project and a restructuring of the network project with increased emphasis on innovation-oriented competency-building activities. While this report mostly reflects our views and reflections as of 2025, the authors of this report have also worked to incorporate earlier lessons and insights from what essentially is a 10-year learning process and the numerous reports and publications that document it.

Digital Life Norway at a Glance

In the course of decade of operation, DLN grew to encompass 50 biotechnology projects with a large network, in particular in the biotechnology community, at the management level at Norwegian research performing organisations (notably universities), and in research policy circles. A continuous challenge for those working for DLN, however, has been to communicate what kind of entity DLN was, and for which purpose(s) it existed. The diversity of the perspectives on DLN (in terms of its functions, roles and understandings) in the Norwegian research and innovation ecosystem is a key aspect for the lessons to be drawn from the DLN experience, and we have structured this report by distinguishing between four such perspectives, to be delineated below. We emphasize both now and later that these perspectives are heavily entangled into each other and that we distinguish between them for analytical purposes only.

The first perspective is DLN as a **network project**. While DLN is described as a national centre for biotechnology research, it is not an organisation in the legal sense, nor a division or unit of an organisation. Instead, in formal terms, the centre was launched as a collaborative project in 2016 between the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU), the University of Oslo (UiO), and the University of Bergen (UiB), led by NTNU and with a 50 MNOK budget funded by the RCN for the years 2016-2020. The RCN funding was renewed (with 50 MNOK) for the period 2021-2026 for what was called DLN 2.0, which expanded the group of project partners with the Norwegian University of Life Sciences (NMBU), Oslo University Hospital (OUS), SINTEF, and UiT The Arctic University of Norway. This collaborative project was originally called the “DLN Network Project” and it contained a competence hub with its own employees

in full or part-time positions at the various partner organisations. The competence hub was responsible for a rich portfolio of DLN services and events, including communication; advice on innovation and commercialisation; data management and use; and responsible research and innovation (RRI). The competence hub was also closely aligned with a (separately funded) DLN research school, and it had its own (advisory) governing structure which included a board with representatives from the project partner organisations and an international scientific advisory board. Furthermore, a project designed for accelerating academic-research intensive biotech innovation (“Innovation Roadmap”, 2019-2026, 30 MNOK budget) was added to and aligned with the DLN portfolio. Below, we shall return to the envisioned “lighthouse” function of DLN, and it is fair to say that it was the network project and surrounding activities that took responsibility and exerted ownership over that function.

The second perspective on DLN is that of building a Norwegian research community, or more precisely as an informal network within the Norwegian research community. It is comprised by researchers who identify with or are associated with the DLN venture – as participants in Norwegian research projects, or as members of the DLN research school, or in other ways (for example, as researchers who also worked for the network project). During the first 5-year period, there were 17 “member projects” that received RCN funding via designated DLN research project calls and as such were obliged to be a member of DLN. Secondly, other Norwegian biotech research projects could join the network as “partner projects”. By 2025, DLN had included more than 30 such partner projects that primarily joined in the second funding cycle. Thirdly, the DLN research school recruited several hundred early-career researchers in Norway, mainly in the biotechnology area. The research school, the network project and the previously mentioned concomitant research project “Res Publica” were key actors in building and organising DLN as a community.

The third perspective on DLN is the expectation that DLN, whatever it was, should deliver research outcomes and innovations and create outcome and impact in terms of structural change in the Norwegian biotech R&I sector (above all the development of new competencies and skills in the Norwegian research community but also new research collaborations). In DLN 2.0, this implied collaborative efforts towards industry, other academic actors and also non-academic stakeholders. Primarily, this perspective refers to the research conducted by the 17 member projects and their participants alongside the new member projects not part of the initial 17 projects from the first funding cycle. To assess impact in terms of structural change, however,

it may also be relevant to consider the associated projects and beyond in the Norwegian biotech R&I ecosystem.

Finally, the fourth perspective on DLN is that of being a research policy experiment, designed and initiated by the RCN to achieve a transformation in the Norwegian biotechnology sector. This is the explanation for why DLN can write such a “Lessons” report that builds on a continuous 10-year learning process. This process included not only a concomitant research project but also regular dialogue events between the RCN and DLN (the so-called “policy forum”) and even a dialogue process between the RCN and potential hosts of the network project before the call for proposals. The policy experiment ambition was thus explicit from the beginning, and this is why the DLN experience may be important well beyond the ambit of biotechnology.

As mentioned, these four perspectives are strongly connected to each other. Indeed, as a research policy experiment, DLN was expected to become a change agent that would transform the Norwegian biotech R&I sector as a research community and thereby contribute to Norwegian value creation, and the funding of research projects and the network project was the main RCN instrument to fulfil that expectation. To draw lessons from the DLN experience, it is important to recall how the expectation – or theory of change, if one so wishes – was articulated by the RCN in their 2014 white paper that introduced the term “Digital Life” into Norwegian research policy.

Several DLN innovation projects were presented at Nordic Life Science Days to increase visibility of Norwegian biotechnology internationally.

The 2014 DLN Vision

In 2014, the RCN published the white paper “Digital Life – Convergence for Innovation” (The Research Council of Norway, 2014). It described Digital Life as a new flagship initiative that aimed to address two key challenges for the Norwegian biotech sector. First, it argued that the international research forefront was moving towards tighter integration of biotechnology and the life sciences with computational science, engineering and informatics (in short, the “digital”). Secondly, it put forth a broad concept of “value creation” that included societal and environmental value in addition to economic value, in line with the national biotechnology strategy and the objectives for the RCN BIOTEK2021 programme. The proposed solution to these challenges was to create a national centre for research that combined and gradually integrated life sciences with “digital” sciences and moreover with social sciences and humanities, the latter in order to facilitate societal and environmental value creation through the principle of responsible research and innovation (RRI). To describe this solution, the concepts of “transdisciplinarity” and “transdisciplinary integration” were frequently used.

Fig. 1 “Illustration of the scope and content of the Digital Life – Convergence for Innovation initiative”, reproduced (The Research Council of Norway, 2014).

The proposed structure of the national centre was the one that indeed was chosen: a national network of partner nodes around a hub that would host and coordinate what ultimately was called the DLN Network Project. A set of “ambitious research projects” were then to be funded and connected to the national centre. In this way, DLN activities would result in the creation of Norwegian research community with new competencies and skills. This community was imagined to function as a “lighthouse” for the Norwegian biotech sector as a whole, guiding it towards integrating digital sciences and embracing the broader notion of societal and environmental value creation. To implement the DLN vision, the BIOTEK2021 programme dedicated approximately a third of their total budget to it.

The DLN Search Conference and Mid-Term Self-Assessment (2018-2020)

The DLN Network Project as well as the first set of six DLN research projects were launched in 2016. In 2018, DLN’s concomitant research project Res Publica organised a two-day search conference with 32 participants from the DLN research projects and network project to develop a three-year action plan to take stock and help steer DLN towards its goals. The participants identified several needs, including the need to sharpen the concept of and focus on transdisciplinarity; to improve cross-project synergies to build community and added scientific value; to improve collaborations between DLN and industry; and to better anchor the DLN vision and venture within its organisational partners. A large number of concrete actions were identified and implemented in the following years (Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2018).

In 2019, the RCN organised a mid-term self-assessment exercise to inform the next funding cycle of the network project. This included a two-day seminar with 30 participants from the RCN, DLN and the DLN advisory board. A number of strategic dilemmas were identified, most of which revolved around the balance between focus and breadth. The assessment echoed the needs voiced by the search conference and raised the question of whether DLN actually had achieved real transformations in the Norwegian biotech sector. It called for a “gear shift” in the second period of DLN, with a stronger focus on the transformational ambition while also trying to achieve

The Digital Life annual conferences connected the different projects together and brought both young and experienced researchers together, forging new collaborations and connections across Norway.

critical mass so as to be a heavier and stronger actor in the Norwegian biotech sector (Centre for Digital Life Norway, 2019). In 2020, the DLN network project applied for a 5-year continuation (2021-2025) with a revised set of objectives that reflected the recommendations of the self-assessment exercise. As part of the “gear shift”, the DLN portfolio was strengthened by the addition of the 30 MNOK Innovation Roadmap project which included a first, diagnostic part to analyse the opportunities to strengthen academic research-intensive biotech innovation in Norway, and then the main part which scaled up DLN support services to cultivate capacity for knowledge transfer and to help facilitate innovation through a series of pilot projects.

DLN Achievements

Following the historical backdrop, the report proceeds to build on the reflections and main conclusions from the legacy workshop in 2025. It identifies key achievements in each of the four perspectives introduced above: DLN as a network project; as a research community; as a biotech R&I; and as a research policy experiment.

Operating a Virtual Research Centre

As a national centre, DLN was structured with team members employed at three different Norwegian Universities (multiple faculties across NTNU, UiO, and UiB) and biotechnology projects from around the country.

Map of the Digital Life Norway project portfolio.

Years before the COVID-19 pandemic normalised virtual workspaces, the team established routines – including regular physical meetings – for effective remote collaboration and team dynamics. The structure of operational management, both in DLN 1.0 and 2.0, benefitted from having team members with complementary thematic roles, which provided flexibility and independence. (In DLN 2.0, the themes were RRI, innovation, training, communications, and data.) However, this also at times limited cross-competence collaboration. In addition, DLN experienced regular turnover of staff primarily due to the short-term nature of the employment tied to external funding; in total, 39 staff members (i.e., coordinators, senior advisors, original

work package leaders) worked at DLN at some point over the course of 10 years. Moreover, budget staff at the 7 host institutions also changed regularly, which added complexity to the already complex accounting inherent in the centre (and its two related projects). This fluctuation, on top of the geographic separation, made long-term learning and organisational culture-building challenging.

From an operational perspective there were ongoing challenges with both communication, institutional anchoring and strategic direction while coordinating activities (i.e., in particular cross-project activities or research data management initiatives) across several large research institutions. In the context of competition for institutional prioritization and without clear financial commitments and interest from the host organizations to ensure continuity, DLN's mandate as a change agent was bound to be challenging. Having a rather small footprint at each host institution, rather than a unified team at one site, may have led to less visibility. The DLN board, with high-level representatives from the respective partner institutions, was also envisaged as an arena for strengthening institutional collaboration and better coordination of input to national biotech policy. This potential did however only partially materialize.

Likewise, the Expert Task Force (ETF) was established in DLN 2.0 as an attempt to enhance anchoring, with senior-level scientific staff who served as representatives at the 7 host institutions.

Members of the Expert Task Force (ETF), which was established as a part of the DLN 2.0 competence hub, worked to anchor DLN's vision in its seven host institutions: NTNU, UiO, UiB, NMBU, OUS, SINTEF and UiT. Front row: Arnoldo Frigessi (OUS/UiO), Marianne Fyhn (UiO), Roger Strand (UiB), Jeanette Hammer Andersen (UiT), Hanne Haslene-Hox (SINTEF). Back row: Phillip Pope (NMBU), Olav Haraldseth (NTNU), Trygve Brautaset (NTNU), Kjetill S. Jakobsen (UiO), Inge Jonassen (UiB) Susanna Röblitz (UiB)

By contrast, the Junior Resource Group (JRG), also instituted in DLN 2.0, was successful at recruiting motivated liaisons between the competence hub and the community of younger researchers at large and elevating their voices. Advantages and disadvantages of the DLN model should be compared with other models of national centres, such as co-location with a national mandate (e.g., entire team based at a single host institution), when designing future initiatives.

The Junior Resource Group (JRG) acted as a voice for the younger scientists in the center, and the inaugural group in 2021 consisted of Emil Karlsen, Marte Jenssen, Eric Juskewitz, Maria Hesjedal, and Simona Kavaliauskiene.

The centre succeeded in delivering support and advice for which there was a high demand throughout the operational periods 2016-20 and 2021-25. The innovation support activities successfully occupied a niche in the national innovation system, providing innovation advice to researchers working closer to basic research and low Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs), for which TTO support might be experienced as less relevant or unavailable. These activities raised awareness that innovation is a mindset, not confined to a particular TRL. Through innovation coaching and the facilitation of new partnerships, DLN helped several projects progress along the innovation trajectory in an experimental way that represented an alternative to existing innovation support mechanisms in the Norwegian innovation ecosystem. Similar services are now being offered by the University of Oslo's "Growth House" which is said to have drawn inspiration from the DLN approach. Forthcoming deliverables from the Innovation Roadmap project will synthesize its findings into recommendations for the Norwegian bio-innovation ecosystem.

On a similar level, DLN advice and support on data management, use and curation (around the FAIR principles) was a highly valued service among DLN participants. A first in Norway, DLN created the FAIR Data Award in life sciences, which was awarded starting in 2021. RRI advice was amply provided both to existing projects and researchers working on grant proposals, and through dedicated capacity-building events both for DLN researchers in general and RRI practitioners within the DLN network. Finally, the DLN research school maintained high activity levels throughout the period and ended up recruiting Norwegian biotech PhD candidates in unusually high numbers, far beyond the remit of DLN member and associated projects.

Building a National Research Community

DLN established national meeting places through its annual conferences, the research school, and thematic workshops. These meeting places contributed to the emergence of distinct communities:

The operational management team consisted of advisors from UiO, UiB and NTNU. The team varied during the center period and managed different focus areas of the center. Left to right (2021): Randi Elisabeth Taxt (UiB, innovation), Ragnhild Vestrum (NTNU, center management), Marta Eide (UiB data management), Maria Hesjedal (Junior Resource Group), Beate Rygg Johnsen (UiO, innovation), Rosalie Zwigelaar (NTNU, Research School), and Korbinian Bösl (UiB, data management). Front row: Kam Sripada (NTNU, center management), and Liv Eggset Falkenberg (NTNU, Research School).

First, and most importantly, DLN brought into existence a community of early-career researchers who developed a shared identity as DLN PhD candidates and postdocs. This emerged through participation in annual conferences and courses offered by the research school – not only technical courses, but also dedicated courses on transdisciplinarity and RRI. Furthermore, communities of collaboration emerged through fostering of shared identity and interdisciplinary cohesion across early – and senior career trajectories. This community was described as particularly valuable for junior researchers involved in the 17 projects funded during DLN’s first funding period. Importantly, many research school members were not affiliated with DLN-funded projects, and some participated despite limited endorsement from their supervisors. This community may be one of the greatest achievements of DLN and is well documented in detail by the concomitant research by Maria Hesjedal and co-workers (Hesjedal, 2023; Hesjedal & Strand, 2021; Hesjedal & Åm, 2023; Hesjedal et al., 2022; Hesjedal et al., 2020). During the legacy workshop, it was repeatedly expressed how participation in a programme like DLN leaves a lasting personal impact. For example, one formerly early-career researcher described how their perspective expanded, from that of “wet-lab science” only, to engaging with the societal dimensions of research.

Secondly, a smaller, informal techno-epistemic community or network, focused on tools, technologies, and systems thinking in mathematical modelling, bioinformatics, and biotechnology. The DLN Modelling Living Systems workshop series was identified as a formative space for this community of both early-, mid- and late-career researchers.

Thirdly, a smaller, informal transformational community, oriented toward making space and time for foundational questions: “What, why, how, and for whom are we conducting research?” While this community can be seen as a result of RRI work, it included not only RRI practitioners but a number of DLN staff and researchers from all career stages, some of whom devoted considerable time and effort to such questions at DLN events such as workshops and walkshops. A small number of dedicated RCN staff were also active part of this community, contributing to dialogue and learning across the research funding/performance interface.

Fourth, several cross-project collaborations and partnerships emerged through pop-up workshops and funding schemes initiated and facilitated by the network project, enabling networks to form that would not have materialized without DLN initiatives. This was particularly evident in DLN 2.0 without delegated funding to research projects through or with DLN support.

Finally, to some extent a large network was created of the totality of researchers, students and staff participating in DLN network, member and associated projects as well as the research school. To what extent the members of this network shares a common understanding of DLN and a sense of DLN identity, is uncertain but one should perhaps not overestimate the achievement.

Clizia Russotto (UiT) was one of 41 PhD candidates who completed a DLN internship outside of academia. Her internship was conducted at Vectron Biosolutions in 2023.

DLN also achieved some progress in connecting early-career researchers to Norwegian industry. The DLN industry internship programme enabled PhD candidates to spend several months interning at Norwegian life science companies (Juskewitz et al., 2021). The students remained employed by their academic institutions and received an allowance, financed by DLN and disbursed through their employers. Many participants described the initiative as a flagship effort: unique in the Norwegian context, consistently praised by participating students, and illustrative of DLN's capacity to bring universities on board to overcome bureaucratic constraints.

Integrating Computational Methodologies and Biotechnology

As noted above, the RCN envisioned DLN to deliver research and innovation and develop new competencies and skills in Norwegian biotech R&I through a set of "ambitious research projects". Based on the legacy meeting and subsequent communication with DLN Principal Investigators as well as a selection of researchers, an attempt has been made to summarize, categorize and assess the extent to which DLN has made a difference with respect to transforming and improving Norwegian biotech research, as compared to an imagined counterfactual state of affairs if there had been no DLN. It should be noted that a full post hoc impact assessment of DLN was still premature at the time of writing of this report. Indeed, several project activities were still ongoing, in particular Innovation Roadmap. A comprehensive, methodologically sound assessment of the research and innovation outcomes would have to wait until at least 2030, possibly later.

An operational insight from the network project, however, was the experienced difficulties in aligning institutional priorities with the highly diverse project needs for support and infrastructure. In addition, it was observed how cross-sector and university collaboration among DLN member institutions require more than mere funding for research.

Still, with this limitation in mind, our provisional assessment exercise as of 2025 concluded with the following key achievements:

- A set of high-impact excellent biotechnology research papers in which the added value of DLN is seen in work where ICT tools and data are integrated to answer biotech research questions
- Improved education and training of PhD candidates for jobs also outside academia via industry internships and relevant competence building in the Research school (see also above)

- Interdisciplinarity has become the standard for biotechnology research in Norway
- Implementation of FAIR principles, data management (plan) and RRI principles has become mandatory in Norwegian biotechnology research projects; introduction of the FAIR Data prize
- Increased interest, competence and culture for innovation in Biotechnology research
- Stronger national awareness and collaboration via network and meeting places
- More researchers from more fields do biotechnology research
- It remains uncertain whether DLN contributed it the following ways:
- Increased quality and impact of Norwegian biotechnology research (e.g. overall stronger publications, more prestigious projects, scientific awards, research breakthroughs)
- More innovation and industry collaboration (e.g. start-ups, patents, licensing), as key results from the Innovation Roadmap project are pending project finalization.
- Visibility of Norwegian biotechnology research (public, industry, national/international)
- Better recruitment of young scholars and talents in biotechnology research (national, international)
- Increased investments / funding or new strategic initiatives for Norwegian Biotechnology research
- General increased awareness about the importance and added value of computational approaches (model- and/or data-driven) to biotechnology. Specifically, it is unclear how much can be attributed to DLN and how much to general advancements like AlphaFold.
- Robust networks that enable formation and applying for large centres (SFIs, joint infrastructures, etc). There are several examples where DLN participants are partners, but they might also have been established without DLN.

Finally, DLN cannot yet be said to have contributed to a generally increased competence in the application of digital technologies (modelling, statistics, machine learning, AI) in the Norwegian biotech sector. Although a high number of PhD candidates students have been trained in these areas, there is still a lack in competence among late-career researchers. Many researchers are aware of these methods and would like to apply them because they believe they are beneficial for their research (in academia) or operation (in industry), but they simply do not know how and see limits in their application in particular fields.

A unique activity organized by the RRI focus area was the workshop which combined lectures, discussions and physical challenges over multiple days sparking reflection and deep thinking. Workshops were held in Jotunheimen In September 2019 and Rondane National Park (pictured) in August 2024. (Photo: Marius Widerøe)

Transforming a Research and Innovation Subsystem

The DLN initiative was a research policy experiment and a deliberate attempt by the RCN to transform the Norwegian biotech sector. The achievements and challenges mentioned above, present some evidence for concluding that the experiment did produce some results that may be considered transformative, perhaps above all the creation of a rather large community of early-career researchers who developed a distinct Digital Life identity.

Efforts taken to achieve a deeper anchoring of DLN and its transformative ambition within the partner organisations, above all the universities, were, however, crowned with little success. From the perspective of the Network Project, part of the explanation of the limited transformative aspect was to be found in administrative obstacles within and between member institutions, but also DLN's lack of authority over its project portfolio. It is important to remember, however, that such obstacles can be seen as signs of real institutional resistance against transformation and lack of institutional memory as much as organisational problems for which a quick fix can be deployed.

As of the end of the DLN funding period, it appears unlikely that the partner organisations will support the continued operation of DLN. There is little evidence of strategic uptake of the transformative ambition of DLN, nor its operational practices, in the partners' plans and policies, signalling this lack of institutional memory. It is also difficult to assess to what extent DLN managed to become the "lighthouse" that was expected to lead and change the entire Norwegian biotech R&I ecosystem by shining example. We see this less as a failure and more as evidence against the validity of the metaphor of the lighthouse as a theory of change and transformation. Notably, even if the total funding for DLN research and support activities amounted to around half a billion NOK over a 10-year period, this was in fact only a small percentage of total R&I investment in the Norwegian biotech sector.

In particular, the ambition of creating societal and environmental value through transdisciplinarity and the principle of RRI cannot be seen as fulfilled. Within the network project, RRI practitioners contributed in various ways, not the least in the role of contributing to the overall governance (Völker et al., 2023). With regard to research and innovation activities, however, while RRI was integrated, deployed and held high in esteem across DLN, the intensity level of RRI asked for and delivered within DLN (with RRI activities typically amounting to some 5% of total budget) was often too low to make a real difference. For several of the funded research projects,

RRI appeared to remain a peripheral concern. In a dedicated DLN research policy workshop in 2024, it was concluded that RRI both in DLN and around, although important, cannot be expected to have real transformative force and shift research into a value rationality mode as long as it is deployed at homeopathic doses. This also became apparent with the challenge of interjecting responsible innovation perspectives in innovation activities in DLN 2.0. As for transdisciplinarity, the unequivocal finding of DLN's own research into the issue, was that DLN researchers understood transdisciplinarity to be synonymous with interdisciplinarity, and acted accordingly (Hesjedal & Strand, 2021).

More generally, beyond transdisciplinarity and RRI, the main structural problem for DLN was that the DLN centre qua network project had no authority on the composition of its own member project portfolio for the first five-year period (DLN 1.0), nor any authority over the execution of these projects. Its role remained one of support and advice for projects that were highly defined at the time of proposal submission and that were largely selected on excellence criteria and less in terms of their ambitions to contribute to the transformation of the Norwegian biotech sector. The experiment was not sufficiently radical and committed on the part of RCN (and even less so of the member institutions) to achieve real transformation. While national distribution of research networks provides unique opportunities and strengths, persistent challenges emerged in creating lasting structural value, cultivating institutional memory, and establishing robust cross-institutional engagement. At the same time, in the course of the 10-year period of DLN, the RCN experienced extensive restructuring and downsizing of its organisation which – in spite of explicit transformational ambitions – reduced its capacity to engage in dialogue, learning and transformational processes. The report returns to this issue when discussing the lessons to be drawn.

Lessons From the DLN Experience

PhD students were trained in how to pitch their science at an innovation workshop session held at the Digital Life conference in 2023, Solstrand. (Photo: Ingvild Melien)

On Operating a Virtual Research Centre

1. The DLN experience is proof in principle that a distributed, virtual research centre can provide valuable services for research projects. The distributed centre structure fostered fruitful collaboration among the host institutions and

the RCN, and DLN became a strong national voice in research hearings and policy discussion. This insight was also noted by the Norwegian AI centre report (The Research Council of Norway, 2023)

- 2. There exist clear niches of demand for competencies and support functions hitherto undersupported in the Norwegian R&I system.** In the DLN case, this included support on **data management, use and curation**, especially with respect to FAIR principles, and **innovation support for academic research at low TRL levels**. We suspect that these niches may be relevant far beyond the Norwegian biotech sector.
- 3. The existence and operation of DLN as a virtual centre and network project critically depended on RCN support.** In spite of clear demand and extensive use of researchers in member institutions, attempts failed at securing post-grant financial support from these institutions. Possible lessons from this observation are legion.
- 4. Challenges with institutional anchoring, strategic direction, and operational issues** (e.g., remote workplace, staff turn-over) across several large research institutions meant that DLN's mandate as a change agent was bound to be challenging.

On Building a National Research Community

- 1. The DLN research school created a large community of early-career scientists in Norway with a sense of "Digital Life" identity.** This is a resource and opportunity that deserves further attention in the years to come. It is also a finding that serves as proof in principle that can inspire similar initiatives in other research fields.
- 2. As for community building at more senior levels** of researchers, DLN achievements were predominantly of the type of **"coalitions of the willing"**. We cannot determine whether this proves that force is futile, or rather that DLN observed coalitions of the willing in the absence of authority to impose directive measures.

3. Flexible funding for creative measures at small scale (workshops, seed funds etc) can yield significant results on collaboration and community building.

The combination of such small funds and the operation of a virtual national centre achieved results that otherwise could not easily emerge because of organisational constraints and institutional logics.

One of the projects that joined DLN is Calinhib – Calcification inhibition. The project focused on development of pharmacological treatment of calcification of heart valves and blood vessels using cell biology and artificial intelligence (AI).

On Integrating Computational Methodologies and Biotechnology

1. The DLN experience is yet another **proof in principle that a research project funding scheme**, even with complicated calls and success criteria, can lead to **individual projects with high quality and desired outcomes**, in this case biotech projects with clear computational and digital components.
2. However, cross-sectoral collaboration and more profound change in the research system require more than project funding. It may be a necessary condition that the research funding organisation (RCN in this case) takes the role of a change agent, but it is not sufficient. **The funder cannot pull structural change by its own force alone.**

3. DLN activities over the latter decade have sparked the **interest in innovation and interdisciplinarity within the Norwegian biotech community**. This is an opportunity for further capitalisation and also further monitoring. Proper evaluation of DLN outcomes should be done no earlier than 2030.

The Legacy Workshop held in Trondheim in April 2025 brought together researchers, students, and other stakeholders from across Norway to reflect on the ten years of Digital Life and to collect lessons and insights. (Photo: Yngve Vogt, UiO)

On Transforming a Research and Innovation Subsystem

- 1. The “lighthouse metaphor”** of the DLN white paper implied the expectation that DLN activities could transform the Norwegian biotech sector by becoming an illustrious example. Considering the DLN experience, this metaphor, if taken to be a theory of change, **does not appear plausible**.
- 2. Real transformation at scale requires institutional commitment, in the sense that authority over research activities must be delegated to the transformation agent.** The absence thereof was continuously experienced in the DLN centre. Neither member institutions nor the RCN took the necessary measures to equip the DLN leadership with real authority over its research portfolio. Future experiments should take a more radical and courageous approach.
- 3. Within the existing institutional logics, there are entrenched orders of worth that are in direct tension with transformational agendas and that reinforce business as usual.** On top of this, the outcome of transformational experiments can only be assessed with precision and rigour in a long-term perspective. **Research policy experiments aiming for transformation in an R&I subsystem need stronger anchoring both in the funding organisation and the research-performing organisations.** In particular, institutional collaboration is fragile when not backed by corresponding long-term institutional commitments. In future initiatives, RCN might want to require that grantees document and ensure their continued institutional commitment.

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